

Graphene: Recent advances on its properties, derived materials and synthesis

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Abstract:

Due to its unique structure and interesting properties, Graphene, a single atomic layer of carbon hexagons, has stimulated much research interest. Graphene and the other carbon allotropes and derivatives such as fullerene, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and graphite have been studied extensively due to their unique physical, chemical, thermal, mechanical, magnetic, and electrical properties. The material's tremendous properties are making it a replacement to many traditional materials in many applications. With the development of nanotechnology and nanoscience, various methods have been developed to synthesize and fabricate graphene by using both Top-down and Bottom-up methods. The purpose of this study is to highlight the most recent research on the state-of-the-art of graphene, to elaborate and discuss the properties of graphene, graphene derivatives, graphene synthesis, and future applications, with the goal of providing a detailed resource for scientists, researchers and graduate students from different sectors.

Keywords:

Graphene; Carbon nanotubes; properties;

Growth and Characterisation of Nanonetworks and Graphene Nanoribbons on metal surfaces: Critical Role of Substrate on Atomic Structure

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Abstract:

The absence of band gap in graphene hinders its potential application as an effective component in nanoscale electronic devices. In this context a number of different approaches for generation of a sizable band gap in graphene have been proposed. Recently explored strategies include chemical modification, bilayer control and induced defects [1]. Another promising route for inducing a band gap in the electronic structure of graphene relies on confining the charge carriers within a quasi-one dimensional (1D) graphene nanoribbon (GNR). The electronic structure of GNRs is highly dependent on their geometry and chemical composition: the one dimensional band structure of GNRs depends critically on its chirality (armchair, zigzag or intermediate edge shapes) and the size of the band gap depends inversely on the GNRs width [2]. Despite intriguing electronic properties, synthesis of structurally precise GNRs using top-down concepts remains challenging. However, bottom-up strategies can be effectively implemented for the fabrication of atomically precise graphene nanoribbons (GNRs). Atomically precise graphene nanoribbons (GNRs) can be fabricated via thermally induced polymerization of halogen containing molecular precursors on metal surfaces (Ullmann reaction) [1]. Recently, using 10-10'-dibromo-9,9'-bianthracene (DBBA) as a molecular precursor to grow armchair GNRs (AGNRs) on Au(111), Ag(111) and Cu(111), we have shown that substrate activity significantly affects the dynamics of GNR formation, nonetheless without significant modification of the GNR growth mechanism [3,4]. Here, we compare the on-surface reaction pathways for bromine functionalized molecules on noble metal surfaces to understand the molecular dynamics before growth of GNRs. Evolution of these systems has been systematically studied via a combination of core level X-ray spectroscopies, scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) and theoretical calculations. The results reveal a significant increase in reactivity for the Cu surfaces in comparison with the Au and Ag surfaces. The GNRs, coordinated with bromine adatoms, are able to arrange in long wire-like structures up to 100nm in length, making this system a potential candidate for nanoelectronics and bottom-up device fabrication. In general, by elucidating molecular transformations of DBBA on these different surfaces, we reveal a critical role of the substrate activity and molecular evolution for GNRs bottom-up fabrication process and molecular nano-architecture in general.

Keywords:

Graphene, molecular networks, surfaces, device fabrication, nanoribbons, nanoelectronics, scanning tunneling microscopy, x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

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